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European Climate Policy: One step forward, two steps back

Abstract

In March 2023, far-reaching decisions on climate policy were made at European and German level: A refurbishment obligation for older residential buildings and a ban on combustion engines in the EU, as well as a ban on the installation of new gas and oil heating systems in Germany. However, these measures counteract another important decision taken in December 2022: the extension of European emissions trading to the buildings and transport sectors.

Keywords: climate policy, emissions trading, reform, efficiency

1. Introduction

Recent climate policy decisions at European and German level have led to intense public debate: The planned ban on internal combustion engines from 2035, a renovation obligation for old buildings recently passed by the EU Parliament and the German plans to ban the installation of gas and oil heating systems from 2024 are causing controversial debates. However, the consideration of another groundbreaking climate policy decision of the EU on the reform of the European emissions trading system is regularly neglected. Against the background of the extension of emissions trading to the buildings and transport sectors decided in this context, the planned technology bans or renovation obligations are not only superfluous, they even have counterproductive effects.

2. Reform of emissions trading

The EU's most important climate policy instrument is its Emissions Trading Scheme (EU ETS), which has been successfully in use for the industrial sector since 2005. In December 2022, after long negotiations, the European Parliament, the Council of Ministers and the Commission agreed on a reform of this instrument and in this context decided to also establish emissions trading for the buildings and transport sectors from 2027 (cf. Lerch 2022).

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Other important components of the reform are an increase in the reduction target for emissions from 40% in the current legislation to 62%, a reduction in the free allocation of certificates by 2034 and the introduction of a climate social fund. From the point of view of a catalogue of requirements for sustainable design of emissions trading systems (cf. Rudolph et al. 2012), the EU ETS has already performed comparatively well so far (cf. Rudolph et al. 2018), and the reform measures now adopted involve further improvements in this respect. In particular, the further reduction of free allocations, the tightening of the cap through faster reduction of available allowances, and greater consideration of equity issues through the climate social fund are to be praised. It should also be ensured in future that 100% of the revenues from emissions trading are spent on climate protection, jobs and social compensation and are not used elsewhere to plug budget holes. The concrete design of the compensation of the expected energy price increases is still pending; the German plans for a per capita redistribution via a climate money represent a promising approach in this regard (cf. Rudolph/Lerch 2023).

In principle, the reform project is to be welcomed from the point of view of environmental economics, but the introduction of emissions trading for the buildings and transport sectors is not consistent enough: a separate emissions trading system (ETS 2) is planned for buildings and transport, which will also be subject to a price cap of €45 per tonne of CO₂. Two separate emissions trading systems for the same pollutant (CO₂) make no sense from an economic point of view, because one of the greatest advantages of the instrument "emissions trading" - economic efficiency - is not exploited: This is achieved precisely because the certificates are allocated where the marginal abatement costs are highest, which means that the emissions target is ultimately achieved at the lowest economic cost. However, this presupposes that emission rights can be traded across sectors. Better than a separate system would therefore be the inclusion of the transport and building sectors in the existing EU ETS (a corresponding criticism also applies to the already existing German system of a CO₂ price for buildings and transport, cf. Lerch et al. 2021). For the same reason, efforts to link the EU ETS with other emissions trading schemes worldwide should be urgently pursued (cf. Lerch et al. 2023).

Various reasons are put forward against a single ETS and for the introduction of two separate systems, but they are not convincing overall. The most important argument is that due to the higher marginal abatement costs in the transport and building sectors, allowance prices would also rise for the industrial sector, thus hindering international competitiveness. For this reason, Khabbazan (2022) also comes to the conclusion in his analysis of a General Equilibrium Model that welfare would be higher with two parallel emissions trading systems (ETS 1 and 2, EU_MIX) than with a

common system (EU_Full): "In addition, the results suggest that moving from the EU_MIX to the EU_Full scenario may decrease the overall welfare. The underlying reason is the slight loss of international competitiveness under the EU_Full scenario." (Khabbazan 2022, p. 3). However, this is not a contradiction to the argument of efficiency gains through a uniform system presented here, because Khabbazan also sees lower overall avoidance costs in the latter.

The problem of the "slight loss" of international competitiveness should therefore not be countered with the inefficient separation of the CO₂ market, but on the one hand, as already emphasised above, with an increasing international linking with other already existing emissions trading systems (e.g. in the USA or perspective also in China, cf. Lerch et al. 2018), as well as on the other hand with a border adjustment for the countries and regions in which no CO₂ pricing has taken place so far (such a border adjustment is, incidentally, envisaged anyway within the framework of the reform of the EU ETS).

3. Dirigiste measures: Within the framework of emissions trading not only unnecessary but harmful

Contrary to widespread assumptions, the adopted or planned dirigiste measures (bans on certain technologies or the obligation to renovate old buildings to make them more energy-efficient) do not bring about any additional emission savings when the transport and building sectors are included in emissions trading and are therefore unnecessary from a climate policy perspective. As is well known, this environmental policy instrument ("cap and trade") is a so-called "quantity solution" in which first the total quantity of emissions is limited to the desired level ("cap"), then emission rights are distributed to the emitters in the amount of the cap (preferably by auction). In the next step, the emitters can then trade these rights among themselves. The object of this trade, however, is not the total amount of emission avoidance (this is determined by the cap), but only its distribution among the emitters. This is precisely how it is ensured that emissions avoidance takes place where the avoidance costs are lowest, which ultimately achieves the emissions reduction target at the lowest possible cost to the economy as a whole (see above).

If one now additionally introduces a ban on combustion or heating or a renovation obligation for old buildings, one does not achieve any additional emission savings because the emission rights that are freed up by this are used elsewhere for emissions - the total amount remains unchanged (this is the well-known "waterbed effect"). Moreover, such additional bans or obligations are even harmful because they massively hinder the great advantage of emissions trading - efficiency. For then it is no longer the abatement costs but the state that decides where emissions abatement takes place. In

relation to the CO₂ savings that can be achieved, the energy-efficient renovation of old buildings is extremely complex and expensive, heat pumps are not suitable for all residential buildings, and the ban on combustion engines hinders the necessary technological openness in the development of future efficient mobility solutions.

However, the efficiency of climate policy is ultimately decisive for its success: only if the greatest possible CO₂ savings are made per euro invested does there stand a chance of achieving the climate policy goals. Or to put it another way: we simply cannot afford an inefficient climate policy. Moreover, the planned measures - as the heated debates currently show - also diminish the acceptance of climate policy among the population.

4 Conclusion

To sum up, one has to state: The most recent climate policy decisions at both European and German level appear paradoxical: a fundamentally welcome agreement on the extension of emissions trading at the end of 2022 was followed in spring 2023 by several, ultimately counterproductive decisions on dirigiste market interventions, which prevent the hoped-for and necessary increase in the efficiency of climate policy. It seems as if policy-makers do not trust their own positive course-setting.

References

- Khabbazan, M.M. (2022): The EU's Gain (Loss) from More Emission Trading Flexibility—A CGE Analysis with Parallel Emission Trading Systems. *Journal of Open Innovation Technology Market and Complexity*, 8, 91. <https://doi.org/10.3390/joitmc8020091>
- Lerch, A. (2022): Reform des EU-Emissionshandels - Licht und Schatten, in: *WiWi Online* (Hrsg.), Online Wörterbuch der Wirtschaftswissenschaften, Hamburg, URL: www.wiwi-online.de/Lit.../768
- Lerch, A., Rudolph, S., Dellatte, J. (2018): Klimaschutz Made in China, in: *Ökologisches Wirtschaften*, Jg. 33, Nr. 2, S. 8.
- Lerch, A., Rudolph, S., Ikkatai, S., Kawakatsu, T., Aydos, E. (2021), Nachhaltiger Emissionshandel Im Verkehrssektor. Eine kritische Bewertung des deutschen Brennstoff-Emissionshandels unter besonderer Berücksichtigung der Erfahrungen in Kalifornien, in: *Zeitschrift für Umweltpolitik und Umweltrecht*, 44. Jg. (2021), S. 1-13.
- Lerch, A., Rudolph, S., Aydos, E. (2023), Von regionalen und nationalen Kohlenstoffmärkten zu einem globalen Kohlenstoffmarkt: Perspektiven einer Verknüpfung von Emissionshandelssystemen, in: *Herlyn, E., Lévy-Tödter, M., Fischer, K., Scherle, N.* (Hrsg.): *Multi-Akteurs-Netzwerke: Kooperation als Chance für die Umsetzung der Agenda 2030*, Wiesbaden 2023, S. 255-271.
- Rudolph, S., Lerch, A., (2023): Klimageld als politisches Instrument: Für einen sozial gerechteren Emissionshandel, in: *Ökologisches Wirtschaften*, Jg. 38, Nr. 1, S. 9.
- Rudolph, S., Lenz, C., Lerch, A., Volmert, B. (2012), Towards sustainable carbon markets: requirements for effective, efficient, and fair emissions trading schemes, in: *Kreiser, L., Sterling, A.Y., Herrera, P., Milne, J.E., Ashiabor, H.* (Eds.): *Carbon Pricing, Growth and the Environment. Critical Issues in Environmental Taxation*, Vol XI., Cheltenham/Northampton 2012, S. 167–183.
- Rudolph, S., Aydos, E., Kawakatsu, T., Lerch, A. (2018), How to Build Truly Sustainable Carbon Markets, in: *The Solutions Journal*, Vol. 9.